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Dolga Poljana 57
5271 Vipava
Slovenija

Glavni kontakt

E-pošta: zalozba.perfectus@gmail.com

Glavni urednik

Darko Lacmanović, Črna gora

Odgovorna urednika

Bojan Macuh, Slovenija

Pedja Ašanin Gole, Slovenija

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QUALITATIVE RESEARCH OF MEDIA LITERACY IN SERBIA

Gabriela Radetić <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4171-3691>¹

Summary:

Research question (RV):

1. How familiar are citizens with the term media literacy and how do they define it?
2. Media habits of citizens/members of the surveyed target groups?
3. What is their role and contribution in the media literacy process of Serbian citizens?
4. What are the obstacles that currently exist in society and what are the recommendations for future work on media literacy of citizens?

Purpose: To compare the difference in the understanding of media literacy between civil society, the media and educators.

Method: We researched on an in-depth qualitative analysis of the audience.

Results: It does not mean that there are no media and journalists who are credible and who try to satisfy the public interest, but that it is necessary to critically examine the nature and importance of the content of all media, especially those that are available on a daily basis.

Limitations/further research: We suggest to check the applicability of the findings with additional interviews and on a larger sample, i.e., on a wider population.

Keywords: media literacy, types of media, information literacy.

KVALITATIVNA RAZISKAVA O MEDIJSKI PISMENOSTI DRŽAVLJANOV SRBIJE

Povzetek: Cilj raziskave je bil ugotoviti, kako dobro državljani Srbije poznajo pojem medijska pismenost in kako ga opredeljujejo. Prav tako smo ugotavljali, kakšne so njihove navade glede spremljanja in rabe medijev ter kako sami prispevajo k večji medijski pismenosti Srbov. Raziskovali smo, s kakšnimi ovirami se trenutno srečujejo v družbi, in jih povprašali, katere izboljšave predlagajo za povečanje medijske pismenosti državljanov Srbije v prihodnosti.

Namen raziskave je bil prikazati razlike v razumevanju medijske pismenosti med javnostjo, mediji in izobraževalnimi ustanovami. V ta namen smo izvedli poglobljeno kvalitativno analizo, s pomočjo katere smo ugotovili, da verodostojni mediji in novinarji, ki se trudijo zadovoljiti interes javnosti, sicer obstajajo, a kljub temu menimo, da je potrebno medijske vsebine bolj natančno raziskati in kritično oceniti, še zlasti tiste vsebine, ki se v medijih pojavljajo dnevno.

Glede na rezultate raziskave predlagamo, da se uporabnost raziskave preveri z nadaljnjimi raziskavami in dodatnimi intervjuji, ki naj se izvedejo na večjem vzorcu oz. širši populaciji.

Keywords: medijska pismenost, vrste medijev, informacijska pismenost.

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¹ School of Advanced Social Studies, Gregorčičeva ulica 19, 5000 Nova Gorica, SI Slovenia, gabriela.radetic@gmail.com

Introduction

Media literacy mainly refers to the ability to access, analyze and create media content and is an extremely important topic in the 21st century. Considering the great importance of media and new media technologies in modern society, it can be said that there is no literacy without media literacy. In this sense, the most important concepts of media literacy include issues of authorship and structure of media messages, as well as creative techniques used to create media texts.

Media and information literacy is one of the basic dimensions of moral and civic education. It is also the basic right of every citizen in every country of the world and thus enables everyone to protect their privacy and find their place in a society whose technological environment is changing faster and faster (Aufderheide, 1993 – Audrey Azule, Director General of UNESCO, at the International Consultative Meeting on Curricula for Media and Information Literacy held on September 13, 2019 in Belgrade, Serbia).

In the 1970s, UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) began to emphasize the importance of media education, putting it on the list of its priorities. At the International Symposium on Media Education held in 1982 in Grunwald (Grunwald, Federal Republic of Germany), the participants adopted the first Declaration on Media Education, when the advocacy for the systematic development of media literacy at all levels of education, on an international level, began (UNESCO, n. d.).

In Serbia, more than 80 percent of households have access to the Internet, and 78 percent of residents aged 16 to 74 can be considered regular Internet users, according to the analysis of the Republic Institute of Statistics (Milojević & Ružić, N.Vajzović, 2021).

On the other hand, the Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications has determined through its research that more than 51 percent of the population over the age of 15 do not have any of the basic skills in the field of information and communication technologies, such as sending and receiving e-mails, internet searches, word processing and others (Kuzmanović et al., 2019).

In Serbia, in the last five years, media and information literacy has become the focus of public discussions both in the media and information sector, and in the IT sector, however, although more attention is being paid to media and information literacy, this area is still underdeveloped (Media Education Center Belgrade, 2017).

Although media strategies represent an important part of a country's media policy, the first media strategy in Serbia (for the period from 2011 to 2016) was adopted only in 2011. Nine years later, in 2020, a new "Strategy for the development of the public information system in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2020-2025" was adopted and it represents the strategic plan for the period from 2020 to 2025. Within the framework of the new Media Strategy, the development of media literacy is set as one of the main goals of the Strategy. Apart from this document, media literacy is recognized as an important area of public interest in the new set of media laws adopted in 2014 (Media Education Center Belgrade, 2017).

Media literacy was defined at the conference in Aspen in 1992 as "the ability of an individual (citizen) to access, analyze and produce information for specific outcomes (Aufderheide, 1993). Patricia Aufderheide in front a group of media experts gathered around the Aspen Institute defined media literacy as "a movement that expands the concept of literacy to include the powerful post-print media that dominates our information landscape which helps people understand, produce and negotiate meanings in culture of powerful images, words and sounds" (Aufderheide, 1993). Media literate person, everyone should have the opportunity to be that, can independently decode, evaluate, analyze and produce contents of both printed and electronic media (Aufderheide, 1993).

Research methodology

We researched on an in-depth qualitative audience analysis. This method is not as precise as a quantitative survey, but it gives an insight into the wider context of the problem, where we can have the possibility of interaction of all participants, polemics and finding possible solutions.

The research was carried out in Novi Sad (the multinational capital town of the province Vojvodina) in the period -2021 and was conducted with representatives of the four target groups that we determined as the most relevant for this research, namely:

1. Representatives of civil society organizations: Among the representatives of civil society organizations, the most represented were representatives of organizations dealing with culture, entrepreneurship, the IT sector and workers in production.
2. Media representatives: In the focus group, representatives of media and media workers were represented by representatives of print media, radio, television (public service) and online portals.
3. Representatives of educational institutions: Educators who participated in the research were primary and secondary school teachers.

Selecting focus group members

The elements we paid attention to when selecting participants are:

1. Representation of different ages.
2. Equal or approximate representation of the sexes.
3. Different levels of education.
4. Representation of representatives of civil society organizations with different fields of activity in focus
5. Representation of representatives of different types of media
6. Representation of members of different educational institutions
7. Representation of persons with disabilities,
8. Representation of national minorities, i.e., participants whose Serbian language is not their mother tongue

Media habits of focus group respondents

At the beginning of the focus groups, all participants filled out an anonymous questionnaire that listed the types of media and their most relevant or most popular representatives. The questionnaire served as a basis for the discussion that was conducted within the same segment and which served as an introduction to further discussions and deliberations.

The table shows the most common ratings for each individual media within each of the focus groups, where rating 1 represents the option "never follow this media", 2 "rarely follow this media", 3 "occasionally follow" and rating 4 "regularly follow this media".

Figure 1: Media habits of focus groups regarding the types of media

Regarding the types of media, we noticed that the focus group media and media workers follow all sources of information the most, but this is due to the type of work they do in order to hear and see as much information as possible. Civil society generally prefers websites and social networks, but not completely to follow them regularly, but to keep up to date with some information. As for the focus group of representatives of educational institutions, on average they follow all the media, but this is for the sake of education in order to keep up to date with information due to the transmission of it in classes.

Figure 2: Printed media followed by civil society

As for the printed media, we came to the conclusion that the daily newspaper "Dnevnik" has an advantage over the others, but that is because it is a local newspaper and in them you can get information about events in the city.

Figure 3: Local TV stations followed by focus groups

As for TV stations, education workers follow RTS the most and it has an advantage over other stations, but that is the situation at the moment due to Covid-19, where the school program is broadcast via RTS television. The media follow TV stations where the programming scheme is designed to be informative and entertaining, and as far as civil society is concerned, watching TV stations in general is poorly represented.

Figure 4: Radio stations followed by focus groups

Civil society mainly follows radio stations where the programming scheme is music and fast news. The media, on average, a little bit at a time, and the educational focus group gave varied answers, but on average very weak. According to the opinion of all three focus groups, radio is a medium that has recently been used only for entertainment, i.e. listening to music.

Figure 5: Social media followed by focus groups

Social networks are, on average, the most represented of all media. Everyone agrees that there you can see and hear the widest range of information in the shortest and fastest time.

The participants of all three focus groups showed no confidence in the media that comes out, i.e. are broadcast in Serbia REM (Media Education Center Belgrade, 2017). Based on the results of the polls and the discussion, it could be concluded that the media, such as public services or certain print media and radio stations, lost their loyal audience due to distrust in the truth and objectivity of their information.

They see the insufficiently active functioning of non-independent regulatory media bodies as a big obstacle, because they are most responsible for the bad media scene we have today, and they should be the ones who should take care of what is read, watched and listened to today.

Print media is increasingly being forgotten. Research shows that newspapers are the last source of information that focus group members rely on.

Definition of media literacy

Within this segment, the interviewees of the focus groups independently wrote their own definitions on pieces of paper and how they understand media literacy, and then a discussion was opened, after which joint conclusions were adopted.

The three most frequently mentioned definitions:

1. Searching for information in order to make personal conclusions
2. Using the media as an aid in self-education
3. Comparing the same information from different media to get the real state of reality (Media Education Center Belgrade, 2017).

Other definitions of media literacy:

1. *Media literacy is the knowledge and use of various technologies, basic as well as advanced programs that are present today*
2. *A critical attitude towards the messages that the media sends us.*
3. *Ability to access, analyzes, evaluate and produce messages in different communication forms*
4. *Use of media content for different interests*
5. *Using media devices as a means of obtaining information*
6. *Understanding context and media messages.*
7. *Recognizing propaganda and manipulation in the media.*
8. *Using the media for social cohesion*
9. *Informing through the media*
10. *Media literacy refers to the ability to 'consume' and think critically about information obtained through mass media such as television, radio, newspapers, and today the Internet.*

Participants of all focus groups were well acquainted with the term "media literacy" in its broadest sense. Through the discussion, it was possible to conclude that this term in the educational sense is most often confused with information and communication technologies, competencies and the very art of using new technologies, but the common conclusion is, nevertheless, that the emphasis is on cultivating critical thinking and understanding media messages and the intentions of their inspirers and the creator.

Which factors influenced their Media literacy?

Within this segment, the participants individually expressed their opinion on the question **"what factors influenced their media literacy?"** All respondents answered that, in addition to parents, schools play a big role in media literacy of children, which can provide children with work in school newspapers or radio and television studios, thus preparing them for the opportunities, challenges and dangers of the Internet and other media.

We asked that each focus group separately answer the question: **"What is their role in the further media literacy of people and in what way will media literacy in society be more successfully realized and developed?"**

Civil society representatives answered that media literacy is very important for developing critical and self-critical attitudes. It is important to raise social awareness to a level that will enable them to act more successfully in different areas of interest, as well as to apply different methods for more productive achievement of professional and personal goals. They are of the opinion that there is a great and crucial need for the most professional and mass education of people, so that different areas such as sectors and systems that decide the paths of society, influence cultural elevation as well as awareness of human rights, sectors of the production of informative programs, manuals and other factors on which more mass influence and the need for media literacy depend. In addition, more educational methods of applying mass media should be considered within educational systems.

The basic role is to raise public awareness, followed by an educational component that can be implemented within thematically diverse projects and activities dealing with human rights, culture, creative industries, entrepreneurship, etc. Also, they emphasize the need and possibility of producing different educational and informative material.

Of course, in the syncretistic of the media and the general public, they believe that the key to achieving a more conscious and diligent development of the adoption of media literacy, because without those two coexisting factors, it would not be possible to educate or empower the public for the need and application of media literacy.

Media representatives agree that none of the mentioned factors has a self-existent role or function in one common goal, the achievement of media literacy for the general public. Additionally, they believe that citizens' trust in the media is of key importance, as

well as the need for the media to be directed towards raising awareness among citizens regarding the need for media literacy, and they are also of the opinion that citizens have lost trust in the media.

Creating media content basically refers to decision-making (journalists, editors, communicators) and selection. For example, when creating a newspaper article, a journalist chooses words and sentences that represent the event they are reporting in the "best" or most reliable way. Of course, the choice of words and sentences is adapted to the editorial policy of the media or other and different interests, which unfortunately are not always in accordance with the ethical principles of the profession or what is called the public interest, i.e. the audience's interest in having accurate and reliable information. In addition to choosing words and sentences, journalists also choose photos to publish with text or frames to "cover" the event. And here, again, there is a possibility to present the same event in different ways, by choosing appropriate recordings or photos. The point is that the contents of traditional mass media are actually only a reflection or representation of the reality created as a result of various influences, and not the raw untouched reality that the media supposedly only mediates. This does not mean that there are no credible media and journalists who try to satisfy the public interest, but that it is necessary to critically examine the nature and importance of the content of all media, especially those that are available daily.

On the other hand, the media expressed an appeal for higher education of people, i.e. the influence of the education system to bring forth in people a more expert individual critical attitude in relation to the information offered by different media, as well as to create the need for them through a more comprehensive education. For media literacy in order to understand and search for adequate information, and in order to critically and self-critically perceive reality.

Through the statements of *representatives of educational institutions*, we concluded that they are aware that they are the key factors with the greatest responsibility in relation to media literacy. They pointed out that school managers are important, and that it depends on how prepared they are in creating a working atmosphere within school institutions, as well as creating conditions, procurement of funds to enable their employees to work more innovative methods. Lecturers are ready to use dialogic methods to emphasize the need for media literacy among students, some have declared that they use new tools in lectures and draw attention to media literacy in formal education. It is very important to protect students from dangerous media content and point out the dangers lurking. Through an interactive approach, individualization and team work with students, a more attractive and progressive way of acquiring material and knowledge in general is created. They believe that more effective methods of applying media literacy tools within the existing teaching units in the Serbian education system should be considered within the educational system.

Conclusion

For modern man and modern society, society of knowledge, media literacy is necessary.

The contents of traditional mass media are actually only a reflection or representation of the reality created as a result of various influences, and not the raw untouched reality that the media supposedly only mediates. This does not mean that there are no credible media and journalists who try to satisfy the public interest, but that it is necessary to critically examine the nature and importance of the content of all media, especially those that are available on a daily basis.

There are reasons for different audience reactions to media culture, namely: personality type, gender, age, family, class, nation, ethnicity, sexual orientation. Of course, the level of general and media education, political, religious and ideological affiliation, social status, etc. should be added here. All these factors must be taken into account when analyzing how the audience receives and interprets some media content.

As Hobbs points out, the future of media literacy is shaped by today's practices (Hobbs, 2019), so our contemporary actions and the development of contemporary policies and practices in the field of media literacy will shape the future of media literacy.

The advantage of the Internet age, when it comes to researching media effects, is that we can investigate the effects of media culture without spatial and temporal boundaries. At the same time, we can know how audiences on different continents react to the same media content. Of course, there are certain cultural patterns that clearly influence audiences around the world.

The majority of young people find information about the world around them on the Internet and social networks. Research by the umbrella organization of the youth of Serbia showed that 98 percent of young people spend several hours a day on the Internet every day - the average young person on the "net" is three hours and 37 minutes. Only one in four of them watches television every day, and only 16 percent of young people read newspapers every day. Young people between the ages of 25 and 30 are the best informed, half of them watch television every day, and only a third read daily newspapers - points out Boban Stojanović, representative of the Umbrella Organization of Serbian Youth (Đorđević, 2018).

It is not enough to include only the latest media in the learning process. Digitization is only part of media literacy. Media literacy means learning about all media, newspapers, radio, television, knowing their history, production and economic principles of functioning, who owns and controls the media, what is the concentration of media ownership and its consequences - concentration of social power, impoverishment and concentration of content, etc.

The media is neither harmful nor useful, and can be both. Although the public is often concerned with the dangerous and harmful side of the media, excessive violence, pornography, stereotypes, sensationalism, the media can also be a useful source of entertainment and information. Both ways affect the socialization and shaping of the identities of children and adults, and even national identities.

Parents and teachers need media literacy in order to raise children and raise them properly. The media play an important role in the lives of children and families. Media literacy, in addition to the reflective level, encourages the productive level. It is important to enable children to work with the media, at school or at home, to enable them to have a practical understanding of media craft, economic and production policy (Kuzmanović idr., 2019).

Media literacy of parents is very important so that they can guide their children's which media will be used, how and how much, what they want from that media and how to get to it. Children spend an average of three to four hours a day with television and other media, i.e. most of their free time, and they do not have a critical attitude towards media content, so they are more susceptible to its harmful effects.

Not all mass media are bad; we should look at their positive effects as well. "Let's think of the pleasures that the mass media provide us through music, movies, television shows, etc.

We need to have a more balanced approach if we want to become media literate. We should appreciate what is good and criticize and not practice what is bad. Society should not leave the citizens to deal with the numerous media messages that reach us at any moment in an ever-increasing amount, but should start the process of media literacy. When a person is media literate, he is also aware, able to analyze, interpret and properly use the media and their content.

From all of the above, we can conclude that the need for media and information literacy permeates and creates the need for media and information literacy in all areas of today's society. Non-governmental sectors that make decisions to include media literacy in the education system have the greatest influence and performance. In this way, ways would be found for information to flow faster, more accessible, clearer to every member of society in order to facilitate his current affairs or enable new, more innovative project activities. Everyone agrees that through the media today, from various sources, information is available to all spheres of society, regardless of educational level.

Various seminars, programs, workshops are methods that should educate society from the youngest to the oldest age. Of course, despite different opinions and critical attitudes towards innovative approaches, the goal of developing media literacy is necessary in order to enable the population in all areas of social action to achieve their own goals faster and more productively. Due to the need to bring media literacy closer to everyone, to design seminars, workshops, etc. is of crucial importance. Involvement in public debates, implementation in different social sectors, expression of critical opinion, is of great importance. The media's task is to inform and affirm citizens, organizations to create conditions for the acquisition of knowledge through literacy within the media sphere, and civil society to create a positive atmosphere for understanding, need and useful application of information technologies

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